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AI Generated Media Detection: A Multimodal
Ensemble Architecture to Combat Synthetic
Media

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AI Generated Media Detection: A Multimodal Ensemble Architecture to Combat Synthetic Media

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Recommendation Letter from the Thesis Supervisor

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Abstract

Over the past decade, the rise in generative artificial intelligence has accelerated to the point that diffusion models and generative adversarial networks (GANs) now produce such highly realistic videos that are often visually indistinguishable from real footage. Consequently, it has become exceedingly difficult to differentiate between real and synthetic videos. While this technology allows creative uses, it also brings harmful content, the spread of misinformation, privacy violations and fraudulent activities. Current detection methods primarily rely on unimodal spatiotemporal artifacts, which often struggle to generalize to newer generators, particularly failing in multimodal or heavily altered videos. To address these limitations, we propose a novel multimodal ensemble architecture: GenDet26. GenDet26 is designed to detect synthetic videos by extracting cross-modal artifacts across visual and audio domains. It captures visual artifacts, frequency anomalies and acoustic desynchronization via specialized streams to identify the generative patterns existing in the videos. Unlike conventional fusion approaches, GenDet26 utilizes an attention-based gating mechanism to compute a global context vector for each input sample and dynamically weights each modality to optimize classification. We evaluated GenDet26 on a custom dataset comprising videos generated by state-of-the-art models, including Veo3, Kling2.6, Kling2.1, Seedance 1.0, and Openart Lipsync. GenDet26 achieves 96.72% accuracy, 99.43% AUC, and a 96.77% F1 score, outperforming existing baseline models in the multimodal domain. To demonstrate robust generalization, we conducted 5-fold cross-validation, maintaining a strong global accuracy of 94.10% ($\pm 3.8\%$) and an AUC of 0.990 (± 0.007). Furthermore, ablation studies validated via McNemar’s test ($p < 0.001$) statistically confirm the necessity and superiority of our unified multimodal approach over single-modality configurations.

Keywords: Synthetic Video Detection, Multimodal Fusion, Dynamic Attention Mechanism, Cross-Modal Generalization, Diffusion Models.

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Above all, we express our gratitude to almighty Allah for making this thesis possible by giving us strength and capabilities to perform our duties.

Dedication

We solemnly dedicate our work to the memory of innocent Palestinian children whose lives were brutally taken by the State of Israel in its ongoing colonization of the Arabian Peninsula. In honoring their memory, we acknowledge the unjustified genocide and stand in solidarity with the thousands of innocent lives lost.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

The evolution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in media, focusing on image, audio, and video modalities, has significantly accelerated over the past decade. After the introduction of Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) by Goodfellow et al. in 2014 [1] the quality of photorealistic image generation has improved to an unprecedented level. It has become difficult to distinguish between real and AI-generated media. Early GAN based models gradually enhanced image quality until the diffusion-based model emerged and marked the beginning of an era of generative modeling. The term "Deepfake" first appeared in 2017 when certain Reddit users started exploiting GANs to create non-consensual adult content in which led to an increase in harmful AI-generated media. As a result, a range of problems appeared such as spread of misinformation, political conspiracies, privacy violations, fraudulent activities and the race between synthetic media generation and their detection. With the rise of diffusion-based models [2] since 2020, these tools can produce so highly realistic images and videos that are very difficult to distinguish from genuine content with the naked eye. Within the ongoing race of hundreds of models and their varying generation techniques demands the development of a generalized detection model to properly distinguish between real and synthetic data. Traditional detecting tools primarily rely on finding visual spatio-temporal anomalies, noise patterns, or the traces left behind by the generative models. These systems typically consist of deep learning (DL) architecture such as Convolutional Neural Network (CNNs) or Vision Transformers (ViT) to detect and classify properly. These models often struggle in becoming a generalized detector, failing to capture temporal anomalies properly, poor performance on unseen data. Furthermore, these detectors cannot perform properly on multimodal analysis on subtle or highly modified synthetic content. To combat these problems, developing a multimodal deep learning model needs a growing demand that can become a generalized content

detector and fulfill all the limitations mentioned above.

1.2 Proposed Solution

The development of such a detector can bridge the gap between static detection methods and the dynamic evolution of synthetic media. It can also provide a robust protection on classifying harmful, altered media in our social media and daily life. To overcome the limitations of existing synthetic media detectors, this thesis proposes GenDet26, a conflict-aware multimodal architecture designed to generalize across image, video, and audio domains. Instead of relying on a single modality or purely spatial artifacts, GenDet26 separates detection into specialized yet complementary streams. By processing visual dynamics through a temporal stream, frequency anomalies through a 3D-convolutional spectral stream, and acoustic desynchronization via a bidirectional autoregressive audio stream, our network extracts a comprehensive forensic profile. Crucially, our architecture adaptively calculates a global context vector for each forward pass, utilizing a gating mechanism to dynamically penalize uninformative streams and amplify anomalous signals on a strictly per-sample basis.

In summary, the primary contributions of this paper are threefold:

- **A Novel Tri-Stream Architecture:** We introduce a feature extraction pipeline that simultaneously analyzes temporal sequence derivatives, spectral frequency anomalies, and acoustic inconsistencies.
- **Dynamic Modality Gating:** We propose an attention-based global context fusion mechanism that overcomes the brittleness of static concatenation by dynamically calculating the weight and importance of each modality.
- **State-of-the-Art Generalization:** Through extensive experimental evaluation on a custom, challenging dataset comprising outputs from state-of-the-art generators (Veo3, Kling2.6, Kling2.1, Seedance 1.0, etc.), GenDet26 establishes a new bench-

mark for cross-model generalization, achieving an AUC of 99.43% and outperforming existing baselines.

1.3 Thesis structure

The following sections provide instructions and an overview to guide readers through the structure of this thesis. The thesis is organized to guide the reader systematically through the research, while also allowing selective reading of specific technical domains.

- **Chapter 2:** Reviews the evolution of synthetic media and deep learning detection frameworks, highlighting research gaps in cross-modal generalization and existing model limitations.
- **Chapter 3:** Describes the custom multimodal dataset, comprising videos from state-of-the-art models such as Veo3, Kling2.6, Kling2.1, Seedance 1.0, and OpenArt-Lipsync.
- **Chapter 4:** Details GenDet26 training specifications, offline feature extraction, and experimental setup.
- **Chapter 5:** Explains the GenDet26 architecture, including model components, layers, parameters, and optimizers for robust detection.
- **Chapter 6:** Presents model evaluation using metrics like Accuracy, AUC, and F1-score, along with hypothesis testing and performance verification.
- **Chapter 7:** Summarizes key contributions and outlines future research directions in synthetic media detection.

Chapter 2: Problem Description

2.1 Problem Statement

State-of-the-art generative AI models (such as Veo3, Kling2.6, Seedance 1.0, and Openart-Lipsync) have reached the quality of photorealistic image generation that erases the boundary between real and synthetic video. Existing frameworks heavily rely on standard Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) or Vision Transformers (ViTs) to search for spatial or temporal anomalies. As modern generators smooth these out so, unimodal detectors easily overfit to their training data and fail in the unseen models. When current models do use multimodal data (e.g., audio and video), they typically rely on static concatenation. They naively treat all modalities as equally important for every single video, which makes them highly brittle when dealing with heavily modified content (e.g., when a video looks visually perfect but has hidden acoustic or high-frequency spectral artifacts).

2.2 Purpose

Based on a comprehensive review of twenty-four research papers, the primary goal of this study is to develop a generalized synthetic media detection framework capable of accurately identifying AI-generated content across multiple generative models and techniques. The research also addresses challenges related to dataset limitations and computational resource constraints.

To overcome these limitations, this work introduces a diversified benchmarking dataset that includes videos generated from multiple state-of-the-art generative models. In addition, this study proposes a multimodal ensemble detection framework designed to outperform several existing detection approaches identified in the literature review. The proposed architecture simultaneously analyzes video data across three distinct domains and integrates

their representations through an attention-based dynamic gating mechanism.

2.3 Previous Work

A total of twenty-four papers were reviewed for demonstration. Table 2.1 illustrates the comparative analysis of these papers.

The evolution of AI content detection reflects a continuous race against increasingly sophisticated generative technologies. This timeline can be categorized into three primary implementation subsets: single-modal visual and temporal detectors, multimodal feature fusion architectures, and advanced cross-modal reasoning frameworks. The initial shift toward a robust generalized detection began with multi-source fusion aimed at capturing cross-domain forgery traces, establishing the necessity of multimodal data [3]. However, many early and parallel models remained constrained within the single-modal visual and temporal category. For instance, spatial feature distance calculations were used to capture temporal artifacts in high-fidelity videos, but these heavily relied on visual encoders and failed on low-quality media [4]. To bypass these unimodal constraints, researchers introduced unified multi-modal large language models (MLLMs); yet, the advance generation techniques leave a persistent gap for the continual adaptation of these models [5]. In structural visual limitations, single-modal detection expanded to address non-face deep-fakes using pre-trained visual frameworks [6] and perceptual straightening [7]. A shared limitation across these methods is their dependency on pre-trained vision models, which restricts domain generalization. To counter this, multimodal feature fusion architectures were developed to utilize complementary audio-visual information, though they were often bottlenecked by class imbalances and selective feature reliance [8]. In single-modal video forensics, data augmentation via wavelet transforms improved realism detection but failed to capture temporal artifacts [9], while Vision Transformer (ViT) models utilizing few-shot learning adapted well to seen data but struggled generalizing to unseen

data distributions [10]. The benchmarking of newly synchronized audio-video datasets highlighted the performance variations across detection methods. Though these datasets remained limited in size and coverage [11], a comprehensive review further emphasized a significant gap in the utilization of multimodality for generalized detectors, advocating for hybrid approaches [12]. Within image and video modalities, models implemented with stepwise face detection and frame aggregation proved resource-heavy and yielded lower accuracy on challenging datasets [13]. To bypass face-dependency, transformer architectures with multiple attention heads were successfully implemented to detect AI-generated images [14]. Simultaneously, models combining spatial RGB detection with optical flow addressed spatio-temporal inconsistencies, though they proved sensitive to preprocessing and struggled with subtle image-to-video manipulations [15]. Expanding on advanced cross-modal paradigms, novel frameworks leveraged local-global attention to weigh audio-visual cues, but incurred high computational costs and were heavily dependent on audio quality [16]. This diversification necessitated new standardized evaluation metrics to align detection performance with human perception [17]. Meanwhile multi-modal architectures incorporating reasoning and spatio-temporal analysis (e.g., text-video) successfully targeted diffusion-generated content, though their reliance on LLMs creates generalization difficulties on unseen data [18]. Self-supervised cross-modal strategies improved the detection of dissonance patterns but suffered from underfitting when processing asynchronous videos [19]. Even highly specialized single-modal techniques -â such as few-shot learning for identifying generator-specific traces [20] or temporal artifact evaluation [21]-â remain vulnerable to evasive modifications and narrow evaluation scopes. To solidify audio-visual evidence, contemporary deepfake frameworks have integrated specific cross-modal alignments [22], NLP-CNN text-image fusions [23], and combined speech-spectral temporal modeling [24]. Despite their sophistication, these multimodal solutions are frequently constrained by asynchronous inputs, reliance on high-quality unimodal training data, and small unvaried datasets. Finally, the integration of late fusion ensemble voting [25] and joint-training streams for audio, video, and synchronization

[26] illustrates the field’s definitive move toward holistic detection. However, persistent weaknesses—such as the lack of emotion-based features [25] and the absence of high-quality, large-scale datasets [26]—continue to challenge the deployment of universally robust AI content detectors.

Figure 2.1: ACC Score on Multiple Datasets Corresponding to Model Used

A comparative analysis of twenty-four studies examines detection models, their techniques, and generalization limitations.

Source	Problem statement	Model, Modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and Solution	Limitation
Tan et al. [3]	Increase of deepfake technologies needs advance detection for cross-domain generalization.	Multi [audio-video]	UADFV, FF++, Celeb-DF v2	ACC: 95.11% AUC: 99.50% AP: 98.50%	Multi-source information and better fusion can capture better forgery traces.	Does not talk about any limitation of any models.
Zheng et al. [4]	Existing techniques struggle to capture temporal artifacts in high-fidelity synthetic videos.	XCLIP-B/16 Single [video]	Youku-mPLUG, Pika	mAP: 98.46 AUC: 93.45%	D3 calculates the L2 distance of spatial features, trained on a small dataset.	Heavily relies on visual feature encoders, cannot handle low-quality videos.

Source	Problem statement	Model, modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and solution	Limitation
Wen et al. [5]	Cross modal synthetic content creates a need of unified detection framework.	Qwen2.5, LoRA Multi [image-video]	So-Fake-Set	ACC: 93.9% F1: 93.7%	Unified multimodal framework with reasoning.	Needs continual adaptation.
Veerama et al. [6]	Detection technique focused on the human faces creates need of a framework capable of handling non-face deepfakes.	VideoMAE, SigLIP Single [video]	VID-AID	F1: 85.1%	Model built on feature extracted from pre-trained visual models and classify based on feature distance.	Relies heavily on pre-trained vision models.
Interno et al. [7]	Pixel-based detector fails detecting temporal inconsistency and needs temporal and perceptual patterns.	DINOv2 Single [image]	VidProM, GenVid-Bench, Physics-IQ	ACC: 90.90-97.06%, mAP: 98.81-99.12%	ReStraV a perceptual straightening approach to accurately classify.	Model also relies heavily on pre-trained visual models.
James et al. [8]	Existing detection models are unimodal and fails to utilize complementary information from cross-modalities.	Xception, DenseNet, MFCC Multi [audio-video]	FakeAVCeleb	ACC: 98.6%, AUC: 98.8%	A robust multimodal detection framework using pretrained audio and visual models	Limited by class imbalance and relies on pre-trained models and selected features.
Corvi et al. [9]	Video forensic detectors detect realistic content but lack in generalization for focusing only high-level artifacts.	Pyramid Flow Single [video]	Panda70M	bACC: 94.3%	Forensic oriented data augmentation technique based on wavelet transform of video frames.	Not designed to capture temporal artifacts, trained by a single model video.

Source	Problem statement	Model, modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and solution	Limitation
Battocchi et al. [10]	AI-based multi-media concerns of widespread misinformation.	Vision transformer Single [video]	Youtube-8m, Sports-1m, Vision, FloreView Socrates	TPR: 95%, TNR: 93%, AUC: 67-96%, ACC: 68-94%	ViT + few-shot learning is used in the model, adapts well in unseen data.	Generalization to unseen data is a limited due to few-shots learning.
Singh et al. [11]	Current deepfake datasets lack accurately synchronized audio-video pairs and detailed labels.	Benchmarked 11 different methods Multi [audio-video]	FakeAVCeleb	ACC and AUC value change in different methods.	First large-scale, racially balanced multimodal dataset with synchronized audio-video.	Limited size and coverage, with future plans to improve dataset maintenance.
Zou et al. [12]	There is lack of generalized video detection technique as per the evolution of AI generated content.	Non-MLLM methods, MLLM methods	Multiple public datasets	Multiple performance matrix has been used	Hybrid approaches on combining multiple single modalities with domain specific detector.	Significant gap in use of multimodality in generalized detector for synthetic media.
Balafrej and Dahmane [13]	Deepfake detectors are resource-heavy, slow, process too many frames, making them impractical for deployment.	CNN, SRNet-based CNN Single [Image]	Celeb-DFv2, DFDC	Celeb-DFv2: ACC: 95.95%, AUC: 99.13% DFDC: ACC: 81.52%, AUC: 88.11%	Stepwise face detection approach, confidence-based frame aggregation for pixel-level artifacts.	Lower accuracy on challenging dataset, and dependence on face detection quality.
Kundu et al. [14]	Existing detection model fails to detect content when no face available and the background is generated by AI.	SigLIP-So400m, MHSA transformer Single [image]	DeMamba, FF++, GTA-V	Attention diversity loss + CE loss: 97-99%	UNITE a transformer-based model with multiple attention heads.	-

Source	Problem statement	Model, modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and solution	Limitation
Bai et al. [15]	Existing methods lack effective generalized detection techniques for AI-generated videos addressing spatial and temporal inconsistencies.	AIGVDet, ResNet50 Multi [image-video]	GVD (Generated Video Dataset)	T2V ACC: avg 91.1%, AUC: avg 96.9% I2V ACC: avg 89.7%, AUC: avg 96.1%	AIGVDet a model combining spatial domain detection on RGB frames with temporal domain detection based on optical flow.	Method depends on accurate optical flow, struggles with subtle I2V videos, and is sensitive to preprocessing.
Wang et al. [16]	Deepfake videos are becoming more realistic, and existing models often fail to generalize or remain robust.	AV-LGNN, EResNet, AV-LGI Multi [audio-image]	FF++, Celeb-DF, DFDC, FakeAVCeleb and ForgeryNet	ACC: 94.2 AUC: 0.95 - 0.97	Novel audio-visual interaction framework with attention to weigh local-global audio cues.	High computational cost, depending audio quality.
Liu et al. [17]	Performance of detection methods and meet semantic goals with given human perception.	–	EvalCrafter, Chivileva, T2VBench	GPT-4V eval, LLM-Score, VIEScore, TIFA, TIGER, ViLBERTScore, COSMic	Highlights importance of AI generated video evaluation as a distinct research area.	–
Song et al. [18]	Existing algorithms focuses on facial forgeries and often fail to identify diffusion generated content.	LLaVA, CLIP, VQ-VAE, IAFA Multi [text-video]	DVF	AUC: 92.0%	MM-Det a multi modal forgery detection with reasoning and spatio-temporal analysis.	Depends on LLM and may face generalization difficulties on unseen data.

Source	Problem statement	Model, modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and solution	Limitation
Oorloff et al. [19]	Most deepfake detectors are unimodal, rely on supervised training of dissonance patterns.	AVFF Multi [audio-video]	FakeAVCeleb	ACC: 98.6%, AUC: 99.1%	Combined self-supervised learning, cross-modal strategy for accuracy.	Depends on audio-visual synchronization, underfit on async videos.
Vahdati et al. [20]	Synthetic video generator leaves different traces than image generators.	ResNet-50, ResNet-34, Xception, DenseNet Single [image]	COCO, LSUN, MIT, Video-ACID	AUC: avg 74%, RER: 76-96%	Few-shot learning detects accurately even after compression of traces left from different models.	Modified synthetic video can deceive the model to capture the traces.
Ma et al. [21]	AI generated video have raised a potential security concern.	CLIP:ViT Single [video]	GVF	ACC: 98.10-99.72%, AUC: 85.87-96.43%	DeCof, detects via temporal artifact, and distinguish on videos properly.	Evaluate based on temporal artifact only.
Muppalla et al. [22]	Current deepfake detectors are mostly single-modal and fail to capture audio-visual evidence.	CAD Multi [audio-video]	FakeAVCeleb TMC Dataset	ACC: 99.20-93.15%, AUC: 99.30-93.67%	Deepfake detection framework with specific signals and cross-modal alignments.	Model may struggle with asynchronous or corrupted modalities.
Vora et al. [23]	AI generated content will become harder to detect using generalized model as the technologies will get better day by day.	BERT, CNN Multi [text-image]	CIFAKE, ML Olympiad Competition	AUC: 83.67%, ACC: 80.67%	BERT+CNN multi-modal by leveraging NLP for text and CNN for image detection.	Smaller, unvaried dataset, working with audio as future research scopes.

Source	Problem statement	Model, modality	Dataset used	Performance matrix	Contribution and solution	Limitation
Salvi et al. [24]	Deepfakes manipulate audio and video, but existing detectors often overfit to unimodal patterns due scarce multi-modal datasets.	CNN, LSTM, MFCC, SVM Multi [audio-image]	FF++, ASVspooF 2019 Evaluation, FakeAVCeleb, DFDC	ACC: 96%, AUC: 97%	Speech and spectral audio features with spatial and temporal visual cues, fused via temporal modeling.	Performance depends on the quality of unimodal training data, can degrade with poor audio-visual
Khalid et al. [25]	Current deepfake detectors are mostly single-modal and fail to effectively capture audio-visual evidence.	MesoInception-4, Meso-4, Xception Multi [audio-image]	FakeAVCeleb	ACC: nearly 100% (audio), 61AUC: 97.96%	Uses pretrained CNNs for visual and audio features, applies late fusion and ensemble voting.	Weaker visual detection, emotion-based features required
Zhou and Lim [26]	Existing deepfake detection methods focus only on visual manipulations, overlooking audio deepfakes and cross-modal inconsistencies.	R (2+1) D-18 CNN, 1D CNN (audio) Multi [audio-image]	FF++, DFDC	FF++: ACC: 97.02%, AUC: 99.65%, DFDC: ACC: 91.01%, AUC: 96.32%	A two-plus-one-stream model that jointly trains audio, video, and sync-streams, uses attention-based feature fusion.	Lack of a high-quality, large-scale dataset was mentioned

Table 2.1: Comparative analysis of existing detection models and their performance with limitations

Chapter 3: Dataset Description

3.1 Motivation for a Custom Dataset

Current literature reveals a significant shortage of high-quality datasets featuring content from the latest generation of large language models. This made us motivated to create a custom dataset consisting state-of-the-art models to make a proper generalized synthetic detector that will perform better in cross-dataset generalization and main high accuracy on unseen data.

3.2 Dataset Description

To evaluate cross-model generalization our dataset comprises of both synthetic and real video sequences. The synthetic videos ($n = 316$) were collected from state-of-the-art generative models, including Veo3, OpenArt-Lipsync, MiniMax Hailuo, Kling (versions 2.1, 2.5, and 2.6), Hedra, Seedance 1.0, and Seedram. Specifically, Veo3 samples were indexed via HuggingFace ShareVeo3, while the remaining synthetic videos were collected from the OpenArt platform.

The 294 high-resolution real videos were sourced from YouTube. All samples were standardized to a temporal duration of 8 seconds. All the videos in the dataset are of max length of 8s for both real and synthetic videos.

Source	Number of Videos
Veo3	220
OpenArt-Lipsync	45
MiniMax Hailuo	10
Kling (v2.1, v2.5, v2.6)	22
Hedra	9
Seedram	4
Seedance 1.0	6
Total Synthetic Videos	316
Real Videos (YouTube)	294

Table 3.1: Dataset distribution of real and synthetic videos

3.3 Data Collection

To preserve high quality artifacts along with proper audio features the synthetic videos were downloaded in .tar file and the real videos were collected from YouTube via FFmpeg with lossless compression. This ensures that the underlying pixel distributions and audio-visual synchronization remain uncorrupted by lossy re-encoding.

3.4 Data Processing

To ensure the detector captures intrinsic traces rather than superficial noise we conducted a data cleaning process by focusing on complex object interaction. Recognizing that many state-of-the-art models (e.g., Openart, Veo3) embed visible logos, we performed targeted watermark suppression. These artifacts were carefully removed using a combination of automated inpainting and temporal cropping to prevent the model from developing a "shortcut" bias where it selectively classifies AI based on the specific watermark in the videos.

3.5 Data Analysis

The final dataset comprises a total of 610 high-resolution video sequences, maintaining a highly balanced class distribution with 316 synthetic samples (51.8%) and 294 real video samples (48.2%). The synthetic subset aggregates outputs from a diverse array of state-of-the-art generative models like Veo3, MiniMax Hailuo, Kling and others ensuring a broad distribution in generation methods and spatial-temporal artifacts characteristics.

Chapter 4: Methodology

4.1 Dataset preprocessing

To ensure uniform input distributions in feature extraction, all video undergo a strict deterministic preprocessing pipeline prior to network inference. Visually, video sequences are decoded using a Decord Pipeline by uniformly sampling the spatial resolution to 256×256 pixels. To capture temporal dynamics, the sequences are partitioned into non-overlapping continuous clips of 16 frames. For spatial-temporal processing, these frames are subsequently center-cropped to a standard 224×224 resolution and normalized using ImageNet channel-wise statistics. Concurrently, the auditory stream is decoupled from the video container and resampled to a strict 16kHz sampling rate using the Librosa backend, ensuring compatibility with standard speech representation models.

Figure 4.1: Dataset Processing

4.2 Offline feature extraction

To mitigate computational overhead during the training phase, we employ an offline feature extraction technique, mapping the raw multimodal data into a compressed, high-dimensional latent space based on the split requirement and stored via gzip-compressed HDF5 archives. The extraction logic is divided into three distinct, modality-specific streams:

1. **Temporal Stream (VideoMAE v2):** We used the pre-trained *VideoMAEv2-Base* to capture spatial-temporal embeddings. Batched 16-frame clips (single video) are ingested, and the final layer’s hidden states are extracted. To distill the representation, we perform a spatial mean pooling across the 196 spatial tokens, yielding a dense temporal feature vector per sequence. The 16 frames are divided by a temporal tubelet size of 2, resulting in 8 temporal steps.
2. **Spectral Stream (Fourier Domain):** To isolate frequency-domain artifacts from generative synthesis, we transform spatial frames into the spectral domain. RGB frames are first reduced to grayscale using the standard luminosity function:

$$Y = 0.2989R + 0.5870G + 0.1140B$$

A 2D Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) is applied, followed by a low-frequency centering shift. The magnitude spectrum is then logarithmically scaled to dampen high-amplitude DC components, formulated as

$$M = \log \left(1 + |F(Y)| \right)$$

Finally, these continuous maps undergo min–max normalization and are bilinearly down-sampled to a fixed 64x64 spatial resolution. After that to capture high–frequency decay characteristic of generative artifacts left by the generation models, we additionally extract 1D radial frequency from the 2D spectrum. By using

Azimuthal Integration, it is partitioned into 8-dim radial bins. Both the spatial 64x64 map and the 1D radial profile are then passed to the downstream classifier.

3. **Audio Stream (Wav2Vec 2.0):** To capture acoustic discrepancies and unnatural vocal synthesis, the *16 kHz* audio arrays are processed using the foundational *wav2vec2-base* model. We bypass the pre-trained projection heads and extract the raw, unpooled sequence of the last hidden states to preserve temporal acoustic features.

4.3 Training methodology

Following the offline construction of the multimodal dataset, the model training phase relies on a Gated late-fusion classification. By utilizing the pre-computed temporal, spectral, and audio embeddings as frozen inputs, to effectively map the high-dimensional, multimodal features into a unified semantic space for AI-generated media detection, we construct a late-fusion neural architecture optimized for cross-modal interaction. The computational graph is truncated, allowing for rapid batch iterations.

The training objective is to map these independent latent representations (feature vectors) into a shared semantic space to differentiate between real physical recordings and synthetic generative outputs. The distinct feature streams are passed through modality-specific layers to align their dimensions before being aggregated via a cross-attention fusion block. The entire network is optimized end-to-end using a standard binary cross-entropy (BCE) objective, paired with an adaptive gradient descent optimizer (AdamW) to penalize the misclassification of AI-generated artifacts.

The foundational architecture independently processes the extracted features by compressing the dense embeddings into a uniform latent bottleneck of dimensionality $d = 64$. To dynamically weigh the importance of each modality per sample, the projected features are aggregated using a Gated Attention Mechanism. This attention block calculates context-

aware scalar weights for the temporal, spectral, and audio streams and allows the network to suppress noisy modalities while amplifying highly certain visual artifacts.

We initialize the base learning rate at 1.8×10^{-4} , a ReduceLROnPlateau scheduler is employed for monitoring the validation loss to dynamically decay the learning rate when improvements decrease. The model is trained over a maximum of 50 epochs with a uniform batch size of 32. An Early Stopping callback is integrated to prevent redundant computation and overfitting.

To force the model to learn intrinsic features across all inputs rather than a singular dominant modality, we introduce a structured Modality Dropout regularization scheme. During the forward pass, entire feature streams, such as the *Wav2Vec 2.0* audio embeddings, are stochastically zeroed out with a probability of $p = 0.30$. This forces the fusion block to maintain robust classification even in the absence of complete multimodal evidence. This process directly mimics real-world scenarios where synthetic videos may lack an audio track or exhibit severe degradation. The standard *BCE* objective is substituted with Focal Loss. This formulation introduces a modulating factor to the cross-entropy criterion.

$$f = (1 - pt)^\gamma$$

This dynamically down-weights the loss contribution of easily classified real videos, and penalizes the network for misclassifying challenging, high-quality synthetic videos.

Chapter 5: Architecture (GenDet26)

5.1 Proposed Model Architecture

The GenDet26 architecture is a 5.76M trainable parametric, multi-branch network that processes high-dimensional inputs through three specialized modalities before converging into a regularized classification head. The tri-stream (temporal-spectral-audio) embeddings map their embeddings and then pass into a standardized 128-dimensional vector, which is then synthesized via an attention-based Gated Fusion mechanism that calculates a global context vector to penalize uninformative modalities. Finally, this fused 128-D tensor is passed into the terminal Classification Head that applies a GELU activation and aggressive Dropout, and performs a final linear projection to output a singular, unscaled scalar logit optimized via BCEWithLogitsLoss to classify properly between synthetic and real videos.

5.2 Multimodal Extraction Backbone

Before the tensors even reach the primary network, the system extracts a high-dimensional representation across the three modalities.

1. **Temporal Modality:** Visual frames are extracted via the *videoMAEv2-base* model, mapping 224x224 crops into dense embedding of dimension 768 in 16 frames per 8s clip
2. **Spectral Modality:** 2D Fast Fourier Transforms (FFT) map grayscale frame variations into a 64 x 64 log-magnitude frequency domain alongside an extracted 8-dimensional radial frequency profile.
3. **Audio Modality:** *facebook/wav2vec2-base* extracts 768-dimensional acoustic embeddings from the *16kHz* waveform.

5.3 Tri-stream Architecture

The GenDet26 model routes these features through specialized independent modules before a gated attention block.

1. **Temporal Stream:** It is designed to capture not just the static frame embedding, but also their sequential derivatives. Given input visual features $X \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 768}$, the network computes temporal gradients of:

$$\text{First-order difference: } \Delta X_t = X_t - X_{t-1}$$

$$\text{Second-order difference: } \Delta^2 X_t = X_t - 2X_{t-1} + X_{t-2}$$

These are concatenated to form an augmented token representation.

$$Z_{\text{aug}} = [X \parallel \Delta X \parallel \Delta^2 X] \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times 2304}$$

A projection layer scales this down to the transformer’s working dimension ($d_{\text{model}} = 256$), followed by layer normalization. A learnable CLS token and a spatial positional embedding E_{pos} are prepended and added, respectively:

$$Z_{\text{in}} = [Z_{\text{cls}} \parallel Z_{\text{proj}} \parallel E_{\text{pos}}] \in \mathbb{R}^{(T+1) \times 256}$$

This is passed through a 3-layer TransformerEncoder featuring 8 attention heads and a GELU activation. The final output vectors pool the classification token and the temporal mean of the sequence:

$$h_{\text{vid}} = \left[H_{\text{cls}} \parallel \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T H_t \right] \in \mathbb{R}^{512}$$

A dense MLP mapping finally compresses this into a 128-dimensional visual vector v_{out} .

2. **Spectral Stream:** The stream receives 5D tensor $F \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 1 \times T \times 64 \times 64}$. The architecture comprises three 3D Convolutional layers, each utilizing a 3x3x3 kernel, a

stride of (2, 2, 2), and a padding of 1. Each operation is followed by 3D Batch Normalization and a GELU activation:

$$S_l = \text{GELU}(\text{BatchNorm3d}(\text{Conv3d}(S_{l-1}))), \quad l \in \{1, 2, 3\}$$

The channel depth expands logarithmically ($1 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 64$), while the spatial dimension is down sampled symmetrically ($64 \rightarrow 32 \rightarrow 16 \rightarrow 8$). The temporal dimension is pooled via a simple arithmetic mean, and the resulting ($64 \times 8 \times 8$) tensor is flattened ($s_{\text{flat}} \in \mathbb{R}^{4096}$). It is then concatenated with an 8-dimensional radial feature vector (p_{radial}) before being driven through a compression MLP down to 128 dimensions s_{out} .

3. **Audio Stream:** Fake video detection relies heavily on spotting audio-visual discrepancies or acoustic synthesis flaws. The AudioStream processes 768-dimensional embeddings via an autoregressive backbone.

The input sequence $A \in \mathbb{R}^{768}$ is Layer-Normalized, then fed into a 2-layer Bidirectional GRU with a dropout of 0.2, mapping to hidden states $H_{\text{aud}} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 256}$. To dynamically focus on the acoustic frames, the network computes a self-attention distribution:

$$E = \tanh(H_{\text{aud}}W_w)$$

$$\alpha = \text{softmax}(EW_u)$$

Where $W_w \in \mathbb{R}^{256 \times 128}$ and $W_u \in \mathbb{R}^{128 \times 1}$. The weighted sum of the hidden states produces a singular 256-dimensional acoustic context vector, which is mapped via Linear and GELU layers to the standardized 128 dimensions a_{out} .

5.4 The Gated Fusion Mechanism

Once the vectors v_{out} , s_{out} , and a_{out} are computed, they must be fused. Simple concatenation risks dimensionality inflation and treats all the signals equally. GenDet26

employs a GatedFusion module to actively penalize less informative streams per sample. The modalities are stacked into a matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times 3 \times 128}$ global context vector h_{ctx} is derived by averaging across the three modalities. This context determines the scalar attention gate for each stream via a learned dense layer and a softmax mapping:

$$h_{ctx} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 M_i$$

$$g = \text{softmax}(h_{ctx} W_{gate}) \in \mathbb{R}^3$$

The final fused 128-dimensional vector is the gate-weighted summation of the three modalities:

$$x_{fused} = \sum_{i=1}^3 g_i M_i$$

This is fed into the terminal classifierâan MLP structured as Linear(128, 64) \rightarrow GELU \rightarrow Dropout(0.4) \rightarrow Linear(64, 1) to output the unscaled prediction logit.

5.5 The Classification Head

The classification head acts as the final decision boundary for GenDet26. It is a highly regularized Multi-Layer Perceptron that takes the 128-dimensional fused context vector x_{fused} and compresses it into a single scalar prediction. The network first projects the 128-D vector into a smaller 64-D subspace to compress the data and isolate the most important features.

The model then applies GELU and provides a smoother curve for negative values. To stop the model from memorizing specific training data (overfitting), a dropout layer randomly turns off 40% of the nodes during each training step. A last linear layer maps the 64-D tensor down to a single, raw scalar value, known as a logit y_{logit} .

$$y_{\text{logit}} = h_3 W_2 + b_2$$

Figure 5.1: Proposed Model Architecture

Chapter 6: Results and Discussion

6.1 Model’s performance

To rigorously evaluate the generalization capabilities of the GenDet26 architecture, the model was subjected to a stratified 5-fold cross-validation. The experimental results demonstrate stability across the multimodal testing partitions. The baseline training result on the custom dataset gives us ACC: **0.9672**, AUC: **0.9943**, and F1: **0.9677**. After the 5-fold cross-validation test, the global results are ACC: 0.9410 ± 0.038 , AUC: 0.9900 ± 0.007 , F1: 0.9462 ± 0.032 .

Figure 6.1: Performance matrices of GenDet26

The accompanying confusion matrix further corroborates these findings, illustrating the model’s minimal false positive rate and highly confident prediction distribution.

1. Training graph:

By analyzing the training graph, we can say that by epoch 12 the model reaches peak

performance. Crucially, after epoch 12, the validation loss does not permanently decouple and skyrocket while the training loss drops to zero. This indicates that the model generalizes well to unseen data and does not suffer from severe overfitting.

Figure 6.2: Training Graph of GenDet26

2. Confusion matrix:

This matrix shows the results for 122 test samples. The model made the correct prediction 58 out of 61 times. Out of all 32 actual fake samples, the model detected every single one of them, resulting in a zero false-negative rate for the AI-generated class. Because the model is aggressive in detecting fake samples, its decision boundary is slightly conservative. As a result, three real videos were falsely flagged as fake.

Figure 6.3: Confusion matrix of GenDet26

3. 5-fold cross-validation:

Analysis of the training and validation curves demonstrates stable convergence by epoch 12, indicating robust generalization without evidence of severe overfitting. To ensure these results were independent of specific data partitioning, a 5-fold cross-validation was performed, achieving a global Accuracy of 0.9410 ± 0.038 and an Area Under the Curve (AUC) of 0.9900 ± 0.007 .

Fold	ACC	AUC	F1
1	0.9836	0.9994	0.9843
2	0.9508	0.9800	0.9516
3	0.9426	0.9862	0.9465
4	0.9590	0.9967	0.9612
5	0.8688	0.9876	0.8873
Global	0.9410 ± 0.038	0.9900 ± 0.007	0.9462 ± 0.032

Table 6.1: Cross-validation performance table

6.2 Per stream importance

In the stream importance test of the classification of GenDet26, the 5D spectral stream contributes the most significant weight, accounting for approximately 48%. This is mainly because generative models frequently introduce high-frequency artifacts, up-sampling noise, and unnatural spectral distributions during video generation. The temporal stream contributes the second highest importance with 37%. This stream augments the visual features using first-order temporal derivatives (ΔX_t) and second-order temporal derivatives ($\Delta^2 X_t$). These features help detect unnatural motion dynamics, localized flickering, and temporal discontinuities. Finally, the audio stream contributes approximately 15%. Although its contribution is lower than visual modalities, it remains useful for detecting AI-generated voices that share synthetic acoustic characteristics. The gated fusion mechanism allows the model to dynamically prioritize the audio stream when it provides strong evidence of AI-generated content.

Figure 6.4: Stream importance graph of GenDet26

6.3 McNemar’s Test explanation

To evaluate the contribution of individual modalities in the proposed multimodal detection architecture, an ablation study was conducted comparing single and dual-modality configurations against the unified Baseline GenDet26. The Baseline achieved the highest overall performance with an accuracy of 0.975 and an AUC of 0.997. Single-modality configurations, specifically Temporal-only and Audio-only, exhibited catastrophic and statistically significant performance degradation according to McNemar’s test ($p < 0.001$). Interestingly, the dual-modality visual model (Temporal + FFT) maintained strong predictive capability (Accuracy: **0.934**). McNemar’s test revealed no statistically significant difference in predictive errors compared to the baseline ($p = 0.182$). Therefore, the Baseline GenDet26 remains the optimal architecture for robust multimodal AI-generated video detection.

Model Configuration	Accuracy	AUC	F1-Score	Chi-Square (1 DoF)	P-Value	Statistically Significant
Baseline GenDet26	0.9754	0.9973	0.976	NaN	NaN	NaN
Stream 1	0.4836	0.8377	0	56.14516	6.73×10^{-14}	TRUE
Stream (1 + 2)	0.9344	0.9744	0.9365	1.777778	0.1824224	FALSE
Stream 3	0.5163	0.9491	0.6810	50.41667	1.24×10^{-12}	TRUE

Table 6.2: McNemar’s test result

Chapter 7: Conclusion

This study presents a robust and highly sensitive classification model capable of distinguishing between real and AI-generated videos. By solving the limitations of static, unimodal spatial detection, GenDet26 successfully leverages a tri-stream feature extraction pipeline and an attention-based dynamic modality gating system to provide high accuracy in video classification. Comprehensive tests confirm that the model generalizes effectively to unseen data without any overfitting. It achieved an AUC of 0.9900 ± 0.007 , demonstrating exceptional capabilities of feature separability. This model also performs exceptionally on cross-domain generalization based on the challenging custom dataset featuring state-of-the-art 2026 generators, including Veo3, Kling2.6, and Seedance 1.0, confirming the architecture’s exceptional cross-domain generalization. Ultimately, GenDet26 demonstrates that by employing adaptive, multimodal technologies and rigorous training methodologies, even the most hyper-realistic synthetic media can be accurately identified.

7.1 Limitations

Despite the promising performance of the proposed multimodal architecture, several practical and resource-based limitations must be acknowledged. The computational scope of this research was physically restricted by the use of a single NVIDIA RTX 4050 6GB GPU. This hardware bottleneck limited the maximum batch sizes, temporal sequence lengths, and the ability to fine-tune larger spatial-temporal backbones. The evaluation is also constrained by the current lack of large-scale, publicly available datasets featuring high-fidelity, state-of-the-art (SOTA) video generation models from 2026. The most advanced text-to-video generators currently dominating the landscape are heavily restricted behind paywalls, closed APIs, or strict commercial terms of service. Even though our dataset contains some of the SOTA models, GenDet26 fails to learn from a proper

large-scale dataset and might overfit in future improved models.

7.2 Future Work

Moving forward, our primary objective is to scale the foundational capabilities of Gen-Det26. To achieve this, we plan to significantly expand our training corpus to encompass over 10,000 diverse, high-fidelity AI-generated and real videos. Furthermore, to ensure the model does not overfit to the idiosyncratic signatures of specific generative algorithms, we will conduct comprehensive cross-dataset generalization checks.

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